

ISic0312

Inscribed statue base for Lucius Rubrius Proculus

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

volcanic

Object

statue base

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Autopsy

Prag 2018-07-06

Last Change

2021-01-06 - Jonathan Prag edited from notes, photographs and Korhonen edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Found in the excavation of the foundations of the 'Cappellone' of the Chiesa di S.Agata la Vetera , in 1767, and transferred to the Biscari collection.

Coordinates

37.507077, 15.083852

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 1335

Physical Description

Rectangular block of black lava stone. All four sides are cut straight and the block appears to be intact. On the upper surface a depression across the rear half, flanked by two holes for metal clamps adjoining the rear edge, suggests both that a second block stood at the rear and that something, presumably an honorific statue, stood on top.

Dimensions

Height 78 cm

Width 83 cm

Depth 36 cm

Layout

Four lines of Latin text, centred on the stone and filling the face, slightly decreasing in size from line 1.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Large, plain, deeply cut letters. P is open, R and B are closed; some upright strokes (all letter I, some L and V) have a serif ascending upper right; plain interpuncts in lines 1 and 3; the numeral in line 3 is marked by a mid-bar.

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 120-130 mm

Line 3-4: 90-110 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: Not recorded mm

Text

1. L(ucio) · Rubrio

2. Proculo

3. Iivir(o) · quin(quennali)

4. auguri

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

To Lucius Rubrius Proculus, quinquennial duumvir, augur

Translation (it)

Commentary

The only attestation for Catania of a duumvir quinquennalis

Digital identifiers:

TM 491519

EDR 139968

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